

→ MESS0042: Operator Skillset Inventory

MESS 0048

MIMS 2.8.42 - The C Team; a complete sorted list and a discussion of the OP in female operators in action fiction, as well as the difference in alpha vs. beta male presentations; with ancillary discussions on skillset inventories.

[Also: introducing the Next Future Soldier¹ ² (part 1)]

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

February 2023

Best Viewed At: <https://bit.ly/3Yv4yQR>

Brought to you by: Resilient Way American Institute³

Keywords: Next Future Soldier - fiction - special operations - action - heroes - strategy - Ghost Recon

¹ Figure 1 ([gif](#)) - "Magnetic View" firefight between Special Forces and terrorists behind cover, with technicals; credit: Ubisoft

² [YouTube](#) GHOST RECON FUTURE SOLDIER Gameplay Walkthrough Part 1 FULL GAME [4K 60FPS PC] - No Commentary

³ www.rwainstitute.org | a private, invitation only organization for patriots and servicemen.

ABSTRACT

C team values/scores (452.21) are not lower, on average than the B team (398.53); and therefore this group provided excellent new data! In this paper, the author is able to compare the scores by gender (M=440.6, F=505.2), and alpha male (448.87) vs. beta male (423.94). The goal of this is to look for patterns that affect the creation of the “Next Future Soldier.”⁴ Presently ideas for the FS include advancements of the same ideas that make John Rambo the “Rambo” gold standard, or they include technology or multiple capabilities. Which is the right path forward for the propaganda of the young soldiers, male or female, and which is the correct type of NFS? Also, as this paper shows, there is a clear OP bias for female operators, probably as a diversity play; especially in Japanese culture (where anime has a massive power-female standard⁵). Therefore we have to wonder what will be the realistic role for women to play in the NFS era, in our (and our allies’) special operations and groups with unique capabilities? Are we putting way too much expectation on women to fulfill these averages that are clearly out of plausibility for most women?⁶

Finally, What can be done in mimsically defining the Next Future Soldier⁷, and the Next^{Next} Future Soldier? What does the author recommend for the armed services, JSOC, SOCOM, MARSOC, and foreign marines, etc.? What about the creation of a *real* inventory, and a SpecOps “Budokai” tournament? Can the different *teams* work together long enough to work to create this inventory, and the competitions necessary to provide **real** data, preferably with a log4 level of resolution (100 points by 100 skills; or decimals available, as in an Olympic scoring system, with 1000 skills possible, resulting in a log5 resolution)?

Regarding the overpowering of female fictional characters, while they are OP, in fact, their ridiculously high standard deviation of 127.5 skill points and small sample size makes it difficult to know why. Black Widow’s score is unreasonably high compared to The Major - a head-to-toe cyborg - and there is no way Widow can beat Motoko in a straight fight. This goes to show that the property's age/development, as well as well-roundedness matters. It’s probably also true that Disney overpowered her for her movie, as part of an agenda, whereas Motoko Kusanagi had a reliably accurate score (for an anime character). Also, since the non-operator Batman⁸ had the only score over 700, and BW is closest to his score, it may simply reflect comic book bias. But the low scores of Captain America and Wolverine put doubt into this explanation. At any rate, the author will spend some time parsing this issue.

⁴ MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to the Art of War

⁵ [The 22 Best Anime With Overpowered Girls To Watch - Bakabuzz](#)

⁶ Not to be offensive, the author, with all his martial arts and boxing skill scored only ~280, lower than a cartoon character!

⁷ Figure 2 ([gif](#)) - The Future Soldier (as envisioned by Ubisoft’s Ghost Recon); credit: Ubisoft

⁸ Batman Zero Lima Force

Introduction	4
Table 1 - Character, property/age, Score and XP	7
Table 2 - Scores by Gender and Alpha or Beta Male; with avg and Standard Deviations.	9
Discussions	13
Alpha and Beta Males in Action Fiction	14
Overpowered Females; not necessarily a matter of Toxic Feminism!!	15
Implications of Gender Roles, Expectations, Realism vs. Optimism	17
Creating Real Inventories - Advisement to the CENTCOM/SOCOM	19
A Special Operator “Budokai” tournament; who is the “best of the best of the best”?	20
The Next Future Soldier (NFS)	21
The Next Future Soldier Platform (RWAI proposal)	21
The Next ^{Next} Future Soldiertm (N ² FS)	23
References	25
Appendix A - Logos of the Real Branches/Divisions/LEA and Fictional Agencies/Programs featured in this study.	28
Non-fiction	28
Fictional	30
Appendix B - Meet the C Team	31

Introduction

In the previous work, the author examined fictional action characters in two teams, A and B tranches, which are the first thought of and second thought of top-tier operators, respectively. The A team did perform higher in the author’s self-designed inventory system (based upon a 1000-point possible grid, 100 skills with 10 points each; 0 and 11 are also optional).

However, in this analysis, the author wanted to prepare for the next paper, about the American Institute’s⁹ “Next Future Soldier” and operator, by understanding the “C team” (named for order, not lack of skill) and the role of women in action fiction. The author also wanted to know if there was a serious pro-female bias in action movies, as it seems with a plethora of new action roles since Salt in 2010. To determine if there is a “Mary Sue” phenomenon in special operator/spy action fiction, the author is comparing averages and standard deviation values among males and females. Also, the author has divided the males across all three teams into alpha and beta groups; where the betas are less “extra” and more introverted by personality, etc.

Avg Score vs. Organization

Figure 3 - Avg Score by Organization (updated); credit: author¹⁰

* Note that the main programs have nearly leveled out as sample sizes increased; right around 456-460.

** Special programs lost their edge, and USMC is now only behind by a small 50-60 point gap.

⁹ www.rwainstitute.org

¹⁰ SpecOps Skill/Ranking

Figure 4 - Score performance by Special Group; credit: author

Figure 13, Score vs. Name

Figure 5 (13 in first paper) - Scores by name, with error bars; credit: author

Table 1 - Character, property/age, Score and XP

Name	Property	Age of property	Score	Ratio	Short XP	Multiplied XP
Batman	Batman/DC	84	724	8.62	6240	524160
Black Widow	Marvel/MCU	59	675	11.44	7722	455598
Snake	Metal Gear Solid	27	611	22.63	13827	373329
Jack Bauer	24	21	609	29.00	17661	370881
The Major	Ghost in the Shell	34	604	17.76	10730	364820
Nomad	Ghost Recon	22	580	26.36	15291	336402
Sam Fisher	Splinter Cell	21	566	26.95	15255	320355
Snake Eyes	GI Joe	41	565	13.78	7786	319226
Boba Fett	Star Wars	43	563	13.09	7371	316953
Frank Castle	Punisher	49	553	11.29	6241	305809
Jake Sully	Avatar	14	543	38.79	21061	294854
John Kruger	Eraser	27	514	19.04	9785	264195
Gray Man	Gray Man series	14	511	36.50	18652	261128
John Clark	Tom Clancy's	30	511	17.03	8704	261120
James Reece	Terminal List	5	492	98.40	48413	242065
Ethan Hunt	Mission Impossible	27	490	18.15	8893	240111
John Rambo	First Blood series	41	477	11.63	5549	227509
The A Team	The A Team	40	476	11.90	5664	226560
Jason Bourne	Bourne series	21	473	22.52	10654	223734
Aaron Cross	Bourne series	11	459	41.73	19153	210683
Wolverine	X-men	49	459	9.37	4300	210700
Bryan Mills	Taken	14	456	32.57	14853	207942
Frank Moses	R.E.D.	13	455	35.00	15925	207025
Equalizer	Equalizer series	9	454	50.44	22902	206118
Jack Jr.	Campus series	20	453	22.65	10260	205200
Sgt. Jack Carter	Marine series	27	450	16.67	7500	202500
Bob Swagger	Shooter	16	449	28.06	12600	201600
Captain America	Avengers/MCU	82	447	5.45	2437	199834
James Bond	007 series	60	446	7.43	3315	198900

Jack Riley/Conrad	The Condemned	16	441	27.56	12155	194480
Salt	Salt	13	441	33.92	14960	194480
Mary Watson	Sherlock Holmes	36	430	11.94	5136	184896
Scott Mitchell	Ghost Recon	22	429	19.50	8366	184052
Robocop	Robocop	17	425	25.00	10625	180625
Casey Ryback	Under Siege	31	423	13.65	5772	178932
Harry Tasker	True Lies	29	412	14.21	5853	169737
Dutch	Predator	36	407	11.31	4601	165636
Jack Reacher	Reacher series	22	404	18.36	7419	163218
Kayce Dutton	Yellowstone	5	398	79.60	31681	158405
J.P. Mason	The Rock	6	396	66.00	26136	156816
Lara Croft	Tomb Raider	27	376	13.93	5236	141372
Mike Banning	Has Fallen series	10	372	37.20	13838	138380
John Matrix	Commando	38	362	9.53	3449	131062
Remo Williams	Remo Williams	38	360	9.47	3411	129618
Luc Deveraux	Universal Soldier	31	351	11.32	3974	123194
Egerton	Kingsman	11	346	31.45	10883	119713
Napolean Solo	Man from UNCLE	59	344	5.83	2006	118354
Martin Riggs	Lethal Weapon	36	336	9.33	3136	112896
Scott McCoy	Delta Force	37	335	9.05	3033	112221
John McClane	Die Hard	35	327	9.34	3055	106925
Morris Schaffer	Where Eagles Dare	54	320	5.93	1896	102384
Snake Plissken	Escape From series	42	308	7.33	2259	94878
Sgt Slaughter	GI Joe	40	299	7.48	2235	89400
John Triton	Marine series	26	292	11.23	3279	85254

$$\text{Where } M_{XP} = \text{round}\left(\frac{\text{Score}}{\text{Age}} * \text{Score}\right) * \text{Age} \quad (1)$$

Short XP is the rounded value, and is clearly affected if the property is too new to get an accurate reading. MXP is basically a squaring, but there are missing decimals; and this enables a more precise scoring system that fairly well recognizes the experience and talents, in balance.

*Note that the age of the property is a more precise way of seeing how long a character has had to age and 'finish'; rather than character age, which is variable, and discussions of prime vs. non-prime begin to gray the discussion.

Table 2 - Scores by Gender and Alpha or Beta Male; with avg and Standard Deviations.

	<i>Average</i>		<i>% Diff</i>	<i>Average</i>		<i>% Diff</i>
	440.60	505.20	14.66	448.87	423.94	5.88
Standard Dev.	84.12	127.54	51.62	87.80	79.45	10.51
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>		<i>Alpha Male</i>	<i>Beta Male</i>	
	611	675		611		
	609	604		609		
	580	441				
	566	430		580		
	565	376			566	
	563				565	
	553			563		
	543			553		
	514			543		
	511			514		
	511				511	
	492			511		
	490			492		
	477				490	
	476			477		
	473					
	459				473	
	459			459		
	456			459		
	455				456	
	454			455		
	453			454		
	450				453	
	449			450		
	447			449		
	446			447		
	441			446		
	429			441		
	425					
	423					
	412				429	
	407			425		
	404				423	
	398			412		

	396			407		
	372				404	
	362				398	
	360			396		
	351					
	346			372		
	344			362		
	336				360	
	335				351	
	327				346	
	320			344		
	308			336		
	299				335	
	292				327	
					320	
				308		
				299		
				292		

* Note that Black Widow is now the top operator, by score.

The above data seems to indicate a ridiculously high standard deviation among the female operators; with Salt being probably the actual uppermost limit of a really, really good female operator. I mean, in the movie she rolls off a bridge and lands on a moving truck, then leaps to another truck. But female valgus in the knees almost guarantee that after two or three years of this kind of operating will destroy the female knee/ACL+meniscus, precipitating a breakdown. Also, female hormonal peak is around age 27-28, and afterward back degradation and osteomalacia begin. But top operator performance is in the 30s when training over ten years with multiple tours combines with maturity and adult mindsets which are anti-egocentric.

Too many of the above males, alpha or beta, are "lone wolves" and suffered from a lack of teamwork skillset; and many from the 1980s from any electronics knowledge. But the females, aside from Major Kusanagi, are even worse at being both lone wolves and having an unrealistic knowledge base in electronics, as compared to males. This is completely contrary to what we actually know about male and female STEM proclivities!

Finally, we see in these ridiculous % differences, for example, the higher score of female operators vs. male operators. This is obviously problematic in the literature (and the expectations are way too high for women). By contrast, as expected, the alpha males do perform better than the beta males, although all of the above are alpha among common men! But personality differences aside, the fact that the two groups perform basically similarly only highlights the ridiculousness of the female operators. However, these being fiction there is an excuse for it. After all, Black Widow didn't score as high as Batman! So it isn't necessarily a problem of feminism and "diversity" hires. It is also a matter of the Venus expectations; which is most apparent in anime, where little girls can carry anchors and fight 500 lb men, such as in that recent fever dream: "Interceptor."¹¹

¹¹ JJ Colins is not in this study. She will be in the D team study which is mostly going to be composed of women.

Organization samples

XP

Figure 6 - Special programs samples (updated); credit: author

Spec Ops Inventories

Figure 7 - Skills 8 and above, by Operator (made with Excel), updated; credit: author

Discussions

Looking at the data, we have a number of observations about action heroes in fiction. The Mars-based heroes (Heracleon) are, of course, based around a “Rambo” gold standard. After all, to “go Rambo” is not only a skill point, but a colloquialism¹² about taking over, “kill[ing] everything we see”¹³, being super badass, and saving the day. These are clear Heracleon/Herculean values.

Meanwhile, the Venus-based heroines represent a mixture of a) all the best male values, without, for the most part, the anti-hero or fallen-hero programs/hang-ups, b) the best of female traits, such as *useful* deception, with few of the known, factual traits of failure (listed often in the Bible as an attribute of the “strange woman”¹⁴), such as sexual promiscuity, hysteria, and emotional fragility, and c) the ability to be super motherly and tender while being a vicious killer and “man-eater.”¹⁵ The latter isn’t *only* a feminist fever dream. It is actually how ancient cultures viewed the Medusa/Loki end of the Venus-Mars→Exodus cataclysmic affair¹⁶! So much so that Medusa is even a “hero” in a new Amazon Prime commercial, when she turns a man to stone for winking at a friend¹⁷. Not only is she protecting the friend from an alleged threat, but she is also doing so with ultimate power, and unlimited and consequence-free, psychopathic behavior.

The female operators commonly demonstrate this ‘free-range psychopathy’ in their properties, where they repeatedly get away with dubious behaviors their male counterparts cannot (except the 1980’s mega stars, like Arnold’s characters). For the most part, the male heroes are put into arcs that require the discernment of the difficulty of making these kinds of dangerous and/or bad/unethical choices. Gray-Man, Bourne, and the property “The Terminal List” all attempt to provide the surreal action hero within a realistic setting.

But no one wants to see a female heroine film where the actual abilities are in the low 200s range, where realistically where they would be. Salt’s 441 is probably the upper end; we could add another 100 for Major’s full cyborg body which more or less ensured high computer and electronics scores. But two females scoring over 600, out of only 5 samples... is a clear example of bias in fiction. Then again, it isn’t necessarily a feminist agenda (as they have, for example, at Marvel comics and Disney’s “She-Hulk”). It is most likely a **cultural demand** (supply-side market economics responding to the needs of the public) to see women get back at the statistically more violent males of the world^{18, 19}. Simultaneously scratching a deep subconscious and cultural-DNA need to revisit over and over again the Diane vs. Ares battle²⁰ (of Wonder Woman²¹), as a matter of species level PTSD!

¹² [Urban Dictionary: going rambo](#)

¹³ [YouTube: You Heart Belongs To Jesus, Your Ass To The Corps!](#)

¹⁴ [What Does the Bible Say About Strange Woman?](#)

¹⁵ [YouTube: Daryl Hall & John Oates - Maneater \(Official Video\)](#)

¹⁶ [Investments in Ragnarok](#)

¹⁷ [YouTube: Medusa’s Sunglasses - Amazon Prime Commercial](#)

¹⁸ [Sex differences in crime - Wikipedia](#)

¹⁹ [The 1 % of the population accountable for 63 % of all violent crime convictions - PMC](#)

²⁰ [YouTube: Diana vs Ares \[Part 1\] | Wonder Woman \[+Subtitles\]](#)

[YouTube: Steve dies. Diana vs Ares \[Part 2\] | Wonder Woman \[+Subtitles\]](#)

[YouTube: Diana vs Ares \[Part 3\] Final | Wonder Woman \[+Subtitles\]](#)

²¹ Figure 8 ([gif](#)) - credit: DC / “Wonder Woman”

Alpha and Beta Males in Action Fiction

An alpha male is pretty easily defined - A type, big muscles, takes charge, always a “go” type or “gets it done, first,” type; also: a leader or born leader of men, preferably badasses. A classic example would be John Matrix, or Dutch, men who no one would want to tussle with, if they knew what’s good for them. The beta males are mostly beta in terms of comparison to the alpha male operators; often being thinner, more effeminate in dress and appearance, more stoic, more quiet/dark or a follower, and typically introverted and mysterious. The Gray Man is a classic example; he is quiet, brooding, brilliant and introverted. There are, admittedly, some gray regions. Jack Bauer, Jack Ryan Jr., Solid Snake... these are men who ride the lines. But the author is confident in the division above. It isn’t an exact science.

Figure 9 (gif) - “Hercules in New York” played by **the** super alpha, 8-time Mr. Olympia - the Governator - Arnold Schwarzenegger; credit: FilmPartners

Figure 10 - Cort Gentry, “The Gray Man,” played by the stoic, wooden Ryan Gosling; credit: Amazon Prime

However, what is interesting is that we see the idea that the great, handsome, muscle-bound Heracleian hero, often is less preferable or realistic to what the teams, special forces, and CIA or JSOC actually prefer. It is true that only the best of the best of the best become Deltas, and most of these guys *are* stacked. But often they are quiet guys, enigmatic, etc. Few highly effective men will be like Jason Bourne; but equally few will be like James Bond (uber-mansch), or Aaron Cross, or Napoleon Solo, etc. The tendency is actually probably for real operators at that level to be quiet and calm, even reserved and stoic, where alpha traits of leadership become honed to servant leadership and submission to the mission. But that isn’t often what is advertised by mega egoic personalities - especially Arnold Schwarzenegger and other 80s heroes - who are typically seen as more capable because they are so very alpha.

Actually, in real life, the issues of who makes the best operators are far more nuanced and interesting.²² Primarily it is a matter of leadership through putting others above oneself, and being strong-willed, dedicated to the mission, and dedicated to the teams/culture. Nevertheless, there is some ego associated with the Navy SEALs, particularly the 1st-3rd teams (which are 2nd tier), and less so the sixth team (DEVGRU) which is a 1st tier team. As the jokes go, “How do you know if someone is really a SEAL? ... Wait a little he’ll write a book to tell you ‘everything.’” The “SEAL reveal” has become Hollywood famous, literally giving Green Berets eye seizures from all the eye-rolling.

²² [Special Operations Preparation - Good Candidate](#)
[How STRONG Do You Have to Be for SPECIAL OPERATIONS?](#)
[Which Special Operations Force \(SOF\) is the BEST?](#)

Overpowered Females; not necessarily a matter of Toxic Feminism!!

It would be easy, in [current year] to point the finger at feminism, especially toxic “woke” feminism²³, for why there are so many fake ‘gurl power’ action heroines, like JJ Collins²⁴. Of them, there are only a couple of beloved icons, such as Black Widow, who can “cut the mustard” for the audience. The commonality of all of them: **not** being feminists.

So why do these characters remain overpowered, statistically and via plot armor? It could be a reaction to the 1980s muscle-bound heroes who could do no wrong, but their women were constantly dying²⁵. It could also be the Venus motif idea. More simply, perhaps Hollywood perceived how often women watched action movies and felt there was an untapped market. In a way there was, but it has quickly eroded, and much to the detriment of actually well-built action heroines, like Salt.

Figure 12 (gif) - Gee, I wonder why Hollywood had an easier time selling Tomb Raider sequels?

Enjoy an article about “jiggle physics”!²⁶
Credit: Core Design/Crystal Dynamics

Though A. Jolie plays both characters, the preference for a breast-filled video game hero like Lara Croft just has more market value than even a well-designed character! Meanwhile actress S. Johansson has managed to play both the

top heroines on here, being Black Widow and also Major Kusanagi in 2017’s generally panned “Ghost in the Shell”²⁷ live feature, which was actually pretty decent compared to most female lead schlock. But note that these two women account for 80% of the survey!

Why are there so few power actresses that can actually pull this off? There is one woman - a former MMA fighter - who definitely could, G. Carano. But she did an amazing action movie, “Haywire” which went unappreciated; and later she was fired from Mandalorian. The fact is that several women have played great operators, but rarely as leads, and even more rarely as believable, beloved, and memorable leads.

People just rarely buy into the “Superwoman” vibe, without the unlimited Venetian magic powers, such as those of Wonder Woman or Storm, Jean Grey, etc.!

²³ [MESS0043: The Collectivist Anti-MIMS](#)

²⁴ [the worst name you can call a woman #interceptor #shorts - YouTube](#) << seriously hilariously cringe.

²⁵ The more macho, the more likely they will die; especially women associated with 007 or Jack Bauer.

²⁶ [Jubbies, mammaries and boobs: Discourses of breast physics in video games | Request PDF](#)

²⁷ Figure 13 - Major Motoko Kusanagi, played by S. Johansson; credit: Paramount Pictures (2017)

One actress who could back in the day was L. Hamilton, after “Terminator 2” when she had such a ‘badass’ vibe. But she wasn’t an operator in that movie and failed to capitalize on such momentum.²⁸

Badass

Cringe

In theory this should not be cringe but equality, but in the actual presentation was perhaps one of the worst scenes in recent action movie history. ([gif](#))²⁹

²⁸ In the mid-90s D. Moore did “GI Jane” which is a pseudo-true story about a infantrywoman; but she was never an operator, and this role was, again, agenda driven and political, rather than aciton driven. The story had a message, which is fine, but it could never have led to a believable (or realistic) more permanent operator role.

²⁹ [YouTube](#) Avengers 4: Endgame - Female Avengers Unite! Scene (2019) Movie Clip

Nothing to do with feminism as a failure - which it is. Far more to do with the facts of biological expression via psychology and audience demands³⁰.

For example, the movie “Expendables” *was cringe* for starring so many has-been actors³¹, but did so well that it sparked an entire franchise³². However, **one scene** in “Avengers: Endgame” managed to produce a feminist scene so cringey the audience still groans over it. This is a double standard which is not fair, and yet, it simply **is** cringe-worthy, terrible writing, and undeniably eye-roll inducing. Writers for female action heroines: *don’t do this to your characters!*

Figure 18 (gif) - “Aeon Flux” is the author’s ‘guilty pleasure’; it was at the forefront of a series of sci-fi action heroines which increasingly flopped; due to ever-increasing ((agenda)) and audience fatigue. Aeon flux avoided this fallacy; credit: MTV Films

Implications of Gender Roles, Expectations, Realism vs. Optimism

So the audiences have expectations for their female action heroines which are either so cringey they belay the operator, or so unrealistic they create near ‘Mary Sue’ level scores. What is to be done? Nothing about the latter, and abandon the former. Why? **In fact, men love these OP women!** It’s rare, but sometimes women do, too. Since women tend, biologically and psychosocially, towards codependency³³ and social affability, positive-affirmation, and being low in disagreeability³⁴, these leads tend to threaten women. Major Kusanagi, is a sexy-robot that is bisexual, prefers hot women or super hot males (eschewing her perpetual would-be lover, Batou, despite him being so machismo), and she has no feminist values. She is a meritocracy gynoid, and as dangerous as a hedgehog in a potato gun. This is nothing women want to watch, generally. Mrs. Johansson was doomed in playing her. She had to be asexually-sexualized, plus be the “wrong” race³⁵ (because collectivists don’t understand the source material or art³⁶), and be believably badass, which she *nearly* pulled off with her Black Widow-level grace. However, in the end, she fell flat for men, and could never have pleased female audiences, on average.

Meanwhile, Salt, for example, shares no values women admire. She ruthlessly [spoiler alert] watches her husband die! Black Widow is the **only** main character which is for women, that men can admire, and what did she have to do: atone for her wickedness through self-sacrifice for ‘the children’.

The audience forgave her, for her “red ledger”³⁷... but they wouldn’t forgive Disney for releasing her standalone biopic years later³⁸, and no longer relevant, since the audience knew her as dead³⁹. Disney, and audiences were moving on to the latest flawed psychopathic Venus motif: Scarlet Witch in “Wandavision” which

³⁰ This will be explored more explicitly in the Team D survey.

³¹ [Every Actor Who Turned Down The Expendables](#)

³² [The Expendables Franchise Box Office History - The Numbers](#)

³³ [Depression and codependency in women](#)

³⁴ [Low Agreeableness - Pros, Cons & What It Looks Like - Discussing Psychology](#)

³⁵ [Ghost in the Shell Tries To Own its Whitewashing... And Fails](#)

³⁶ [Is Scarlett Johansson Too White for Anime? Not Necessarily. | The New Republic](#)

³⁷ [The Avengers - Natasha's trick HD](#)

³⁸ [Black Widow review: MCU's latest isn't too little, but it is too late - Polygon](#)

³⁹ [Review: Marvel's 'Black Widow' Is Too Little, Too Late &](#)

[Black Widow's Death | Avengers Endgame \(Open Matte\) \[4K UHD\]](#)

received rave reviews... misleading Disney into thinking audiences wanted something else (like a female Loki, or a snarky “She-Hulk”), when in fact audiences just needed to understand the psychopathic mother who loves them but ruins the world.⁴⁰

Meanwhile the author - me - just wants to see Sarah Connor - level badasses, with Salt/Jack Bauer level competency, well developed like a “Shooter” series or something, believable, but inspiring, and high quality. Don’t give me a “female Jason Bourne”. A *Bournette* is uninteresting, either motif-wise or story-wise. The magick psycho heroine is far more interesting in comparison.

No: give me a Salt-level badass, played by an actual alpha female like G. Carano (but fresh out of MMA), with the right charm and wit, easy on the eyes like Jolie or Johansson (especially her)... and make the story make sense.

- What might work: a female Jack Ryan.
- What probably won’t work: a female John Clark.
- What will work: development and taking time to arc a flawed person, multi-layered and deep (like Black Widow).
- What will not work: snarky one-liners, cringe rants, poses, fights with 250 lb behemoths hand to hand and no deception, tools, or guile, resulting in an injury-less heroine who pretends she will save the day and make waffles, too, and never ruin her marriage.

We all know that when the “Devil Wears Prada” she is *not* good at being a housewife. Realistic CIA roles portraying real-life female analysts (figure 19 above; *badass*) and spies have shared this fact. And those women are brusque and unlikeable; but damn it if they were operators, we’d love them, anyhow. We - the audience that loves everything kickass, will root for that flawed psycho because: **she completes us**.

⁴⁰ People want to explore flawed women, not Mary Sues like Rey from the failed Star Wars Disney trilogy which squandered audience good will, and ruined their own fanbase, so bad that it is probable Disney will sell the ‘golden goose’ off after losing \$65 billion due to these misunderstandings!

Creating Real Inventories - Advisement to the CENTCOM/SOCOM

This paper is only a mere introduction to this topic, but it is time to reveal the main purpose of the work, outside of good, honest critique, and putting science to *science fiction*. The main purpose is that the author would like to see the special operations community create its own specops Olympics. For now, though, we live in a “milsim” [airsoft] world, and it’s probably only realistic to have a single tournament. Essentially the same idea: multiple events, multiple teams, and one winner. To get there, the SOCOM et al community needs to utilize a realistic inventory. This fictional one ain’t exactly it. Although in many ways the spirit of it is. However, there will need to be breach elements, explosives specialties, rigorous training and written testing, diffusing bombs, testing piloting, driving, and otherwise adaptability skills, language and diplomacy skills, etc. Such an inventory will easily exceed the present 3log ceiling (1000 points) and become 4log or 5log; even 6log as these operators refine their scores through “trading card” type stats acquired at gun ranges, competitions in-house, confirmed kills, etc.

The purpose isn’t to increase the vanity of SEAL teams^{41 42}, if they even are the best of the best of the best⁴³. The purpose is to track progressional data which gives CENTCOM actionable inner intelligence on manpower, capabilities for different mission sets, etc. All of these alter both the multi-field array in the 8-domains⁴⁴ (particularly 4 of them⁴⁵), and the “innate Shi”⁴⁶ or disposition within the command structure, and even abroad.

Take the Benghazi situation. Obviously, there were too few men in a bad situation (“Black Hawk Down” anyone?) to expect a perfect survival record and mission outcome. These were also, technically, contractors. Once Delta arrived, actually things calmed down. But the point remains that the men surrounding the ambassador were not top tier, and the better crew of capabilities was restrained at the nearby CIA ‘blacksite’, hamstrung by a career theta male doing CYOA.⁴⁷

Surviving bad situations is hard enough. If people are underperformers, then it will only get harder for all concerned.

We look to action fiction writing to set up the propaganda and expectations these young men (and women) idolize before entering. It screens personalities. How the inventory reveals this information is useful to CENTCOM. But, frankly, to take control of the situation they will need to have **real** inventory data and “player stats” to deal with and to the Pentagon, who can then liaise with Hollywood etc. to design better and better operator figures, and evolve the special operations culture and community *by proxy*. The chest-thumping of various teams, while intriguing, and entertaining for YouTube channels, results only in more bravado, and revelations of real capabilities as people brag and publish; and does not - to the author - result in the kind of “game-changing” advancements we expect from more mimsical examples, like “Ghost Recon: Future Soldier.” Firstly Ghosts are the [fictional] top Green Beret USSOF; they are already the best of Rangers and regular Army. Second, now they are enhanced with new tech and HUD capabilities. Where are these \$multimillion

41

<https://www.businessinsider.com/there-are-nearly-as-many-navy-seal-books-written-as-all-other-special-ops-combined-2015-6?op=1>

42 [Navy SEALs to other Navy SEALs: Don't write books about being Navy SEALs » MobyLives](#)

43 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yj6NAGevRs0>

▶ How Does SEAL Team 6 Compare to the Rest of the Navy SEALs? (Tier One SEALs vs. Tier Two SEALs)

▶ Seal Team 6 vs Delta Force - Who is Better (DEVGRU vs CAG)

44 [MESS0037: MIMS 2.801 - the Eight Domain Array](#)

45 SEAL & Technology; ie: 0-3 [MIMS: Technology as the 0th Domain](#)

46 [Innate Shi of Countries and US](#)

47 [US commandos claim CIA station chief delayed Benghazi rescue | The Hill](#)

support tools for the \$multimillion per operator? New scopes are coming⁴⁸, and they are rumored to be amazing⁴⁹. But that should be continual.

A Special Operator “Budokai” tournament; who is the “best of the best of the best”?

Teams should be not only training, but working on their own sponsorships, especially incentivized to be interested in small company partnerships that result in rapid development programs that adjust to mission parameters fast and not behind a wall of red tape. They should be participating in sponsored tournament events, primarily centering around CQB and CQC skills, and fanning out to sniping, small arms, technicals, survival, recon, SIGINT, computer, and many other types of skills. The tournaments could actually last for several weeks to months, so long as proxies (ie, auditors) oversee data submission, and chest cam footage is tied to competitions, for comparison. The prize? CENTCOM gets a plethora of simulation data, the team or branch gets a bragging prize, and the top operator gets new doors opened up. From training further, to coaching and escaping deadly situations through promotion, to production of new assets and contract advisement. It’s an all-around winning concept, and it could work exactly like any marital arts or basketball tournament. Or a battle robot tournament. If a competition can create an arms race within Battlebots and RobotWars environments, why wouldn’t it work with the most competitive alpha males in the most competitive team environments? And for those that claim they don’t need this or it shouldn’t apply... well this reminds me of all the kung fu “masters” that refused to learn boxing and grappling skills; then got destroyed in the 2010s on camera in cage/ring, by better and more capable fighters. We all ‘know’ or suspect who ‘should’ win, according to our biases⁵⁰, and public persona/propaganda. But traditions about the airborne, or marine corp, or MI6 mean nothing against real-world competition.

Think of it another way. The main branches all have marching bands and rifle teams, etc. Each of those could literally enter marching band and colorguard competitions held by colleges etc. Some would win, and handily. If the damn marching band takes competition and being the best so seriously... why shouldn’t the spec ops teams of all the branches and top allies take it seriously?

Think of it yet another way. If the CCP/Politburo and PLO read this paper, looking for an edge in a hand-to-hand, mano-y-mano fight with the USA and her allies, would they hesitate to **design entire specops teams and branches around competition results after seeing what actually ‘shakes out of the tree’**? No, they wouldn’t. That type of reverse engineering is *exactly* what China would do, and may be doing already; preparing to lack blackops teams in America’s heartland. If they aren’t, then now is our chance to get ahead. Because they do believe their kung fu will create next-level warriors, in body, mind, will, spirit, and ambition. And they are right. Not about boxing skills.⁵¹ They lost those after the era of highwaymen and jianghu truly died away (same as our dueling knights of yore). But what they have now is an increasingly Keen and centralizing motivational force.

Our own SpecOps Olympics, or at least a tournament, could do the very same thing.

Plus the bragging rights for a year could be so much cooler than a single Army vs. Navy football game! Think of the “GI Jane” biopics then! (That’s a win-win-win!)

⁴⁸ [YouTube: The US Military's New Smart Optic that Aims For You. The XM-157](#)

⁴⁹ [YouTube: How the New 'Smart Scope' Changes Combat](#)

⁵⁰ [MESS0045: POS vs. The Deep State](#)

⁵¹ Hence China’s new obsessions with Sanda and Shuai Jiao.

The Next Future Soldier (NFS)

The NFS refers to programs that are not unlike those of the 1990s and 2010s; but a little more centrally sophisticated than the ‘use a smartphone’ solution. It isn’t to take away that. However, there are a lot of limitations to the app-based software development scheme, from support and limitation environments to the unreliability of apps as compared to preprogrammed hardware/firmware. In a flash/CMOS environment, a military-centric app-like (low code) development platform could be incredibly beneficial. More importantly, the way this program interacts with modular hacking and SIGINT attacking programs will be very key. Not only will it need to work with the GPS environment, but will need to actively sense, detect, protect, and provide side distraction for network intrusion events, DDOS, and other events.

Consider this situation, as an example. The high capabilities NFS specops, fresh off his victories in tournament, is sent in with a tier 2 (out of 6) tech kit, meant to nearly blend into difficult environments. They might be after a hard target, or there to surveil a key VIP, or perform routine security detail from a specops level (not attracting attention to themselves). Now, they get in the field, open their apps, and being to surveil the AO. This is the first mistake in the present system. By engaging in the typical 4G/5G environment, or any wifi, they are like a fish swimming in water, making ripples. They can be sighted, digitally, and become a vulnerability point to counter-intel presences, back through the GPS and satcomm network, up and to the point of causing mission failure... if the adversary has a strong digital crew and kit ready to deploy on the assumption they *should make*.

The assumption the adversary should make is that every asshole in a ballcap who doesn’t belong in the AO is CIA and might be wearing a wire, so to speak, connecting them back to the local station or a safe house, maybe even to Langley. This type of ported vulnerability is so typical that it’s taken for granted; again like a fish in water not noticing the water. But in fact, we are getting lucky hiding behind the sheer plethora of data and lack of worldwide capabilities. With AI, though, it would be long before low-code hacks and other weaklings are writing hacking program toolkits, first via chatGPT and Bing, and then making programs that write these tools quickly for them, as a matter of need, depending on environmental (digital/wifi network) variables. Eventually, they *will* discover procedural hacking instances, and the AI daisy-chain of vulnerability productions will accelerate until the operator will be forced to either retreat or revert to a very low-tech spycraft.

That is not ideal in a drone-eat-drone world where, for example, RFID could be used to mark a spy asset, or just any tourist under suspicion, and then your local cartel/terrorist cell-of-asshats ‘drones’ them with a mortar, killing half a dozen others in collateral damage, just to be sure. With the bad philosophy of our adversaries⁵², even Paris could become like Mosul if such capabilities were to become as commonplace as Microsoft Excel. In an environment where the operator loses their edge, merely because we didn’t push the envelope and became dependent on Android or iOS.

What should be in the NFS platform?

The Next Future Soldier Platform (RWAI proposal)

- HUD enhancement via wearable tech
- Bone conduction communications⁵³
- Collapsible, 3D printed backup sidearms (spring fed?)
- Dense, highly collapsable survival knives and tools
- Compacted survival kits with triage and emergency kits

⁵² [MESS0051: POS Philosophy: Islamism](#)

⁵³ [Bone LightWeight Conductor - Roanwell Corporation](#)

- Including miniature AED, and epishots, etc.
- Next-level optics⁵⁴
- Hyperspectral goggles systems⁵⁵
 - Super-NODs having NVG, FLIR, TOS... even sonar (figure 20, right)
 - Signals analyzers built in (visualizers)
- Specialized boot systems
 - Survival, computational, weaponized, and medicine storing
- Advanced ballistic helmet systems (see: Devtac⁵⁶)
 - Helmet storage slots, for types of knives, sim cards, lighters, etc.
- Better, lighter class IV+ plates⁵⁷ and more collapsible plate systems that cover arteries
 - Including femoral and gorgets for the carotid.
 - Is collapsible/unfolding shields a possibility?

Figure 21 (gif) - "Division 2" agent with collapsible ballistic shield; credit: Ubisoft

- Acoustics detection equipment for sonic bombardment or PNCC/neurostrike⁵⁸ warning

⁵⁴ RW "ZooperCam" for military production.

⁵⁵ Figure 20 - "Splinter Cell" sonar goggles gif (uploaded); credit: Ubisoft

⁵⁶ <https://www.devtacdesigns.com/>

⁵⁷ https://www.reddit.com/r/tacticalgear/comments/nghiwr/best_budget_lightweight_lvl_4_plates/

⁵⁸ [MESSr0001 - EMF and Neocortical Astrocytes](#)

- Acoustics defense shielding system⁵⁹
- EM propelled slingshot sidearm system
- Optional collapsible breech and welding torches, plasma cutters, etc.
- Miniaturized plasma lock cutters (“freakin lasers”)
 - And auto-lock-pickers
- “Front packs” for ammo and other means to protect organs
- Aquapacks for the back, designed to distribute the weight along ergonomic vectors instead of pulling on the back.
- Tac-be-gone rapid disassembly engineering to be able to drop for a fight, and re-attach in sequence rapidly again after for redeploy “Oscar Mike”⁶⁰
- Back of the calf storage for fungibles
- Inner pants pockets for personal effects, reducing outer pocket space-waste, freeing them up for mission-relevant McGuffins.
- Bauer style [specially designed] laptop/tac+satchel with added weather and exposure protection, water-proofing and general durability.

Figure 22 - Jack Bauer Bag except this one is crap; see: Amazon⁶¹ ; credit: WarriorTalk.com

The Next[†]Next Future Soldier[™] (N²FS)

The above are externally focused, with a hope and a prayer that the aforementioned competitiveness of the teams’ programs, combined with better-designed characters to incentivize young men and women into becoming “the best they can be”, will lead to much better overall scores.

Again, at the author’s height of martial fitness and skill, he scored around 280, which is lower than John Trtion, despite his limited and monocular development. And worse than a damn cartoon character (Sergeant Slaughter)! Now, the author also did not go to BUD/S or join any branches, and is a civilian (obviously). But the author was high performance in his martial studies and achieved **very** unique knowledge sets. The sciences unlocked, through these studies, yielded new forms of knowledge and data that are capable of enhancing other sets of data. For example, the author uses it to coach youth basketball to perfect seasons, reliably winning - and easily. This science is, furthermore, reliable and anciently based, and yields good mimsical results mingling with modern science and technology stacks. What we must be cognizant of, therefore, is that the issue is only a matter of how to enhance the operators, who are already the best of the best, into becoming a) their personal very best and b) the **best of the best of the best**.

Through systematic analysis, and mimsilation⁶² of the military training issue (as seen in the next MESSy), as well as mimsification of the operator mindset⁶³, etc... we should be able to find the means to take

⁵⁹ [Nanoscale Acoustic Force Field Technology Developed That Isolates Submicron Particles](#)

⁶⁰ Oscar Mike = “on the move”

⁶¹ <https://www.amazon.com/messenger-bag-jack-bauer/s?k=messenger+bag+jack+bauer>

⁶² [MESS0047: the Jewels from Reality Mining... Investigation of MIMS Matrices of Reality with a Realonic Philosoph...](#)

⁶³ [MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to the Art of War](#)

it to a further next level. It's a SPACERS⁶⁴ concept, but not inapplicable. This will create a few rare "John Clark" (*S-Snake!!*) operators that, as Eastwood's character in "Heartbreak Ridge" lovingly said, *"I've drank more beer, pissed more blood, and banged more quiff than all of you numb-nuts put together."*
~GySgt Tom Highway... Oorah

But in this case they will "shit Tiffany Cufflinks"⁶⁵ not in terms of blood and piss and vinegar; but from pure technokinesis, and the ability to drive a nail through "a fly's ass" at 300 m, while moving on a house of methheads like a Delta operator on Red Bull.⁶⁶

All the while they will be engaging with the AI-assisted HUD to analyze the environment for wifi activated IED, or find hackers and their pornhub servers storing American elderly VISA and Social security data, even finding on-the-fly data that connects said methhead POS to a cartel in Bolivia! And if the methhead gets uppity, the NFS - or in this case the N²FS will whip his ass with the fastest "slow is smooth" series of 'springing style' boxing striking, delivering shots so violent, the perp or tango will think they'd been shot by pappy's Colt 1911 .45ACP.

Figure 23 ([gif](#)) - Delta Force Real Training⁶⁷

But in case they have to go almost naked, with only their HUD and some ear comms, at least they will know the vital kidney and carotid→vocal cord regions for a clean *s-slink*⁶⁸ that says "nightie night" to el badguy. That way, our boys (and girls) can come home and make

more oorah babies and barbeques, and - God-willing - enable the good people of the AO's culture to continue living with a few less local POS ruining the world for them. One more chance to protect allies from the dregs of the world, and make the world a place where the few and passive have the chance to actually grow up, attend school, and question POS philosophies like jihadism. Now that's a mission that makes one "love the smell of napalm in the morning." Except instead of burning villagers, we're burning tight mission sets, and remaining kosher by Rules of Engagement and International Law. No one else bothers with that; and that makes all the difference. You can't be a hero by being a villain. **Broadstroke tech stacks harm innocent civilians.** Let's get tight⁶⁹, precise, and vicious⁷⁰.

⁶⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

⁶⁵ ~Gunney "Full Metal Jacket" cc SERGEANT HARTMAN - Full Metal Jacket

⁶⁶ CQB training - Delta Force Hostage rescue - POV

⁶⁷ Just "DELTA Force" Shooting drills

⁶⁸ [US ARMY FM 21-150 - Hand To Hand Combat](#)

⁶⁹ And let's put some self-destruct on those NFS equipment, and prevent our adversaries figuring out our capabilities so damn easy. Make Top Secret Great Again... stop publishing our specops methods to our enemies, FFS!

⁷⁰ SSIVA-PADEP!

References

1. "MESS 0042 - MIMS 2.8.41: Inventory of Special Operator Skills," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/93502619/MESS_0042_MIMS_2_8_41_Inventory_of_Special_Operator_Skills
2. "GHOST RECON FUTURE SOLDIER Gameplay Walkthrough Part 1," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MkNF455-Cjs>
3. "MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to the Art of War," Sf. R. Careaga, 2023,
4. "The 22 Best Anime With Overpowered Girls To Watch," Baka Buzz.com, <https://bakabuzz.com/best-anime-with-overpowered-girls/>
5. "Batman Zero Lima Force," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://bit.ly/3eLPFrG>
6. "SpecOps Skill/Ranking," Sf. R. Careaga, 2023, https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1funHkGWqHVZYSHHX5_6peHDbBydCN1dQnxmKY_Ldsl/edit#gid=244806725
7. "Going Rambo," Urban Dictionary, <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=going%20rambo>
8. "You Heart Belongs To Jesus, Your Ass To The Corps!" Youtube, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x7-lnYzUJec>
9. "What does the Bible say about Strange Women?" OpenBible.info, https://www.openbible.info/topics/strange_woman
10. "Daryl Hall & John Oates - Maneater (Official Video)," YouTube, 2010, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yRYFKcMa_Ek
11. "Investments in Ragnarok Comparisons and Conclusions from the study of Media, Business, and Government investments in End of the World myth, story, and preparation," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/36753646/Investments_in_Ragnarok_Comparisons_and_Conclusions_from_the_study_of_Media_Business_and_Government_investments_in_End_of_the_World_myth_story_and_preparation
12. "Medusa's Sunglasses - Amazon Prime Commercial," Youtube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xlcORI2jMPE>
13. "Sex differences in crime," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sex_differences_in_crime#Worldwide_homicide_statistics_by_gender
14. "The 1 % of the population accountable for 63 % of all violent crime convictions," Social Psychiatry Psychiatric Epidemiology, O. Falk et al, 2014, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3969807/>
15. "Diana vs Ares [Part 1] | Wonder Woman," Youtube, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E833w9eXfr4>
16. "Steve dies. Diana vs Ares [Part 2] | Wonder Woman," YouTube, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MS5oNxCQZWQ>
17. "Diana vs Ares [Part 3] Final | Wonder Woman," YouTube, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xCD0iyXhS1w>
18. "Special Operations Preparation - Good Candidate," YouTube, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=51HLC3FMj0M>
19. "How STRONG Do You Have to Be for SPECIAL OPERATIONS?" YouTube, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=scOpaYLBtx0>
20. "Which Special Operations Force (SOF) is the BEST?" YouTube, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i5X1Rlq8kkI>
21. "MESS0043: The Collectivist Anti-MIMS,," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023, https://www.academia.edu/96483677/MESS0043_The_Collectivist_Anti_MIMS
22. "The worst name you can call a woman," YouTube/Netflix Film shorts, <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/Ge0Fml9snMM>
23. "Jubbies, mammaries and boobs: Discourses of breast physics in video games," ResearchGate, R. Rogers & C. Lieber, 2017, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322891959_Jubbies_mammaries_and_boobs_Discourses_of_breast_physics_in_video_games
24. "Avengers 4: Endgame - Female Avengers Unite!" Youtube, Movie Clip 2019. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AID4fLXZ8uU>
25. "Every Actor Who Turned Down The Expendables," Screen Rant, B. Curran, 2022, <https://screenrant.com/actors-who-turned-down-the-expendables-movies/>
26. "Box Office History for The Expendables Movies," The Numbers.com, <https://www.the-numbers.com/movies/franchise/Expendables-The#tab=summary>
27. "Depression and codependency in women," NIH/Library of Medicine, C Hughes-Hammer, D S Martsolf & R A Zeller, 1998, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9868824/>

28. "Low Agreeableness – Pros, Cons & What It Looks Like," Discussing Psychology.com, E. Loker, 2022, <https://www.discussingpsychology.com/agreeableness/low-agreeableness-pros-cons-what-it-looks-like/>
29. "Ghost in the Shell Tries To Own its Whitewashing... And Fails," Screen Rant, A. Leadbeater, 2017, <https://screenrant.com/ghost-shell-movie-2017-scarlett-johansson-whitewashing-plot/>
30. "Is Scarlett Johansson Too White for Anime?" The New Republic, R. Spaeth, 2016, <https://newrepublic.com/article/132763/scarlett-johansson-white-anime>
31. "The Avengers - Natasha's trick," Youtube, 2017, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OJ5hcwa7KZI>
32. "Black Widow isn't too little, but it is too late," Polygon.com, J. Rivers, 2021, <https://www.polygon.com/reviews/22555657/black-widow-review>
33. "Black Widow's Death | Avengers Endgame," YouTube, / Avengers Movie, 2022, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DG_lhmVKbxU
34. "There have been nearly as many Navy SEAL books written as all the other US special ops forces combined," Business Insider.com, P. Szoldra, 2015, <https://www.businessinsider.com/there-are-nearly-as-many-navy-seal-books-written-as-all-other-special-ops-combine-d-2015-6?op=1>
35. "Navy SEALs to other Navy SEALs: Don't write books about being Navy SEALs," Melville House, M. Krotov, 2016, <https://www.mhpbooks.com/navy-seals-to-other-navy-seals-dont-write-books-about-being-navy-seals/>
36. "5 Key Differences Between Delta Force and SEAL Team Six," YouTube/Us Military News, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yj6NAGevRs0>
37. "How Does SEAL Team 6 Compare to the Rest of the Navy SEALs? (Tier One SEALs vs. Tier Two SEALs)," YouTube, 2023, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xB-h3VTNE_A
38. "Seal Team 6 vs Delta Force - Who is Better (DEVGRU vs CAG)," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x2mcs8R9B60>
39. "MESS0037 - MIMS 2.801: the Eight Domain Array," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023, https://www.academia.edu/95561922/MESS0037_MIMS_2_801_the_Eight_Domain_Array
40. "Technology as the 0th War Domain," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain
41. "CALCULATING THE INNATE "SHI" 勢 OF COUNTRIES USING THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA AS A TEMPLATE 1," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1
42. "US commandos claim CIA station chief delayed Benghazi rescue," The Hill.com, R. Shabad, 2014, <https://thehill.com/policy/international/216748-us-commandos-claim-cia-station-chief-delayed-benghazi-rescue/>
43. "The US Military's New Smart Optic that Aims For You. The XM-157," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f5YWXrZdNpA>
44. "How the New 'Smart Scope' Changes Combat," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iPrIN0Gie-U>
45. "MESS0045 - MIMS 2.85: The Deep State POS Theory; people really hate the CIA & FBI!," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023, https://www.academia.edu/96902126/MESS0045_MIMS_2_85_The_Deep_State_POS_Theory_people_really_hate_the_CIA_and_FBI
46. "MESS0051 - POS: Islamism," Sf. R. Careaga, 2023,
47. "Bone LightWeight Conductor," Roanwell Corp, 2022, <https://roanwell.com/products/headsets/bone-lightweight-conductor/>
48. "Devtac Ronin Ballistic Helmet," Devtac Designs, 2020, <https://www.devtacdesigns.com/>
49. "Tactical Gear Querys," Reddit.com, 2022, https://www.reddit.com/r/tacticalgear/comments/nghiwr/best_budget_lightweight_lvl_4_plates/
50. "MESSr 0001 - Report on Potential vectors of neurostrike/PNCC via NMDA receptor," Academia, J.D. Kines & Sf. R. Careaga, 2023, https://www.academia.edu/96624504/MESSr_0001_Report_on_Potential_vectors_of_neurostrike_PNCC_via_NMDA_receptor
51. "Nanoscale Acoustic Force Field Technology Developed That Isolates Submicron Particles," Sci Tech Daily.com, By Singapore University Of Technology And Design, 2020, <https://scitechdaily.com/nanoscale-acoustic-force-field-technology-developed-that-isolates-submicron-particles/>
52. "Jack Bauer Messenger Bag," Amazon, <https://www.amazon.com/messenger-bag-jack-bauer/s?k=messenger+bag+jack+bauer>
53. "MESS0047 - Investigation of MIMS Matrices of Reality with a Realonic Philosophaether Approach," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2023,

[https://www.academia.edu/97036858/MESS0047 Investigation of MIMS Matrices of Reality with a Realonic Philosophy Approach](https://www.academia.edu/97036858/MESS0047_Investigation_of_MIMS_Matrices_of_Reality_with_a_Realonic_Philosophy_approach)

54. "MESS0049: Operator Skill Enhancement according to The Art of War," Sf. R. Careaga, 2023
55. "SPACERS™, LLC - "Are you a spacer?" EPEMC Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>
56. "Gunney "Full Metal Jacket" -cc SERGEANT HARTMAN - Full Metal Jacket," YouTube, 2016, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y_JbKzIK4dA
57. "CQB training - Delta Force Hostage rescue - POV," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D0xsVIF-Txk>
58. "Just "DELTA Force" Shooting drills," YouTube, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AA1kNGJU1JM>
59. "US ARMY FM 21-150 - Hand To Hand Combat," Field Manual No. 21-50, 1994, <https://www.survivalschool.us/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/FM-21-150-Combatives-1992.pdf>

Appendix A - Logos of the Real Branches/Divisions/LEA and Fictional Agencies/Programs featured in this study.

Non-fiction

Fictional

Appendix B - Meet the C Team

